

Global dispersal and diversity of rust fungi in the context of plant health

Mogens Støvring Hovmøller, Tine Thach and Annemarie Fejer Justesen

Address

Aarhus University, Department of Agroecology, Global Rust Reference Center, Forsøgsvej 1, DK-4200 Slagelse, Denmark

Corresponding Author: Mogens Støvring Hovmøller (mogens.hovmoller@agro.au.dk)

Introduction

The importance of long distance dispersal (LDD) of pathogens infecting humans, animals and plants has often been underestimated, which was emphasized during the global human pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2/coronavirus [1]. In the case of pathogens affecting crop plants, LDD events may also occur more frequently than anticipated because they often remain undiscovered, unless they result in large-scale spread of disease with significant impact on human livelihood and welfare [2,3].

In general, plant disease epidemiology and plant health have received little attention in society, despite high productivity in agriculture being a prerequisite for meeting the demand of 70% increase for food and agricultural production by 2050 [4]. One major obstacle for the detection of LDD events in plant pathology is the lack of regular and extensive pathogen population surveys beyond national capacities (<https://rusttracker.cimmyt.org/>; <https://agro.au.dk/forskning/projekter/rustwatch/wheat-rust-early-warning>), for instance with respect to commonly agreed sampling protocols, analytic tools and timely data sharing and communication [5-7]. The link to an exact geographical and evolutionary origin of an exotic incursion of a new pathogen species/strain into a target area may, therefore, in most cases be difficult to establish. This is particularly the case for aerial dispersed crop pathogens affecting major food crops, for example powdery mildews, rusts and blights, which are not part of the regulatory plant health system [8]. The rust fungi (*Pucciniales*) are the most speciose and complex group of these consisting of almost 8000 species and many more distinct genetic variants, which may be individually adapted to its host at both species and cultivar levels [9-11].

High-impact LDD events involving rust pathogens

In the following, we provide examples of inter-continental spread of rust fungi infecting major crop plants and likely transmission mechanisms in the context of significant and high-impact cases. This area of research has gained increased focus since the emergence of the Ug99 race group of wheat stem rust in East Africa in 1999 [9,10], and increasing inter-continental spread of wheat yellow rust since 2000 [11,12]. These and other events led to the formation of the Borlaug Global Rust Initiative [13,14], which facilitated the onset of multiple, international rust surveillance activities (<https://globalrust.org/dggw/surveillance>), including establishment of the Global Rust Reference Center (GRRC) that receives and analyses samples of rust-infected wheat throughout the year from any country and national rust diagnostic laboratory [6].

The most dramatic impact of LDD of plant pathogens often relates to invasion of new territories, e.g., where a disease or a new pathogen variant is spread to a distant area/continent in a disease conducive environment, including aerial spread of coffee leaf rust (*Hemileia vastatrix*) from western Africa to Brazil in 1970, and aerial spread of sugar cane leaf rust (*Puccinia melanocephala*) from western Africa into the Americas in 1978 (reviewed by [2]). The spreading of the Asian soybean rust (*Phakopsora pachyrhizi*) across the Caribbean from north western South America to the United States in 2004 during Hurricane Ivan represents a more recent example [15].

The spread of yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis*) from Europe to Australia in 1978 is a well-documented example, where urediniospores of a single race variant was carried on clothing of a traveller, where they may persist alive 1-2 weeks under dry conditions [16]. Subsequent molecular analyses and plant pathological race assays of isolates representing the initial incursion suggested a European origin [17]. In contrast, windborne spores were the most plausible explanation for the incursion of new strains of wheat stem rust into Australia in 1969, which was recently confirmed by molecular genotyping of isolates from the original study [18]. Despite wheat leaf rust (caused by *P. triticina*) is widespread, relatively few studies have addressed global diversity and migration patterns of this pathogen [19,20]. The presence of shared genotypes and race phenotypes in more than one continent suggest both past and more recent inter-continental migration events, but the authors were unable to document specific LDD cases based on the available datasets. In addition to these well documented cases, hypotheses about dispersal events have also been based on less detailed data, for example the spread of the yellow rust *Yr9*-virulence in Ethiopia in the mid-1980s, followed by observations of stepwise emergence of the same virulence in subsequent years in the Middle East and on the Indian subcontinent [21,22]. Despite widely cited, this *Yr9* dispersal pathway was never documented by appropriate pathogen sampling and genotyping. More recent research combining field surveys, global meteorological data, and simulations using a Lagrangian dispersion model demonstrated low probability of aerial transmission of wheat rust urediniospores from East Africa to South Asia, whereas dispersal of stem rust from the Middle East via Yemen into Africa within a single year was plausible [23,24]. In China, extensive studies have revealed high genetic diversity and migration patterns between winter survival areas and summer habitats, generally reflecting geographical barriers and cropping practices. In terms of discovery of single step LDD events, most studies have remained inconclusive, probably due to high pathogen diversity [25-27] and low probability of resampling individual genotypes.

Recent inter-continental spread of wheat rust fungi

The incursion and onwards spread of a single strain of *P. striiformis*, PstS1, to North America (2000) and Australia (2002), and the incursion of a genetical almost identical PstS2 strain into Europe and Asia, probably represent the most rapid and widespread dispersal of a crop pathogen to date (Figure 1A). Both strains were adapted to warmer temperatures and exhibited increased aggressiveness, causing epidemics since 2000 in the south-central United States, where the disease was previously insignificant [28,29]. PstS1 was detected in western Australia in 2002 [30,31], with subsequent spread to eastern Australia the following year, crossing more than 1500 km desert area [32]. Later, an identical genotype became prevalent in Canada, where it was first detected in 2005 [33]. PstS2 was first reported in Europe in 2000 [31], where only a relatively small wheat area was affected due to widespread deployment of PstS2-resistant cultivars [34,35]. Subsequent studies indicated East Africa as putative origin of PstS1/PstS2 [12], first detection of PstS1 dating back to an isolate sampled in Kenya in 1974 [36]. The fact that PstS1 has not been reported in *P. striiformis* populations outside North America and Australia since 2000 (except few samples in East Africa) may suggest an

accidental, human-mediated spread of this strain, rather than random airborne spore movements around the globe between 2000 and 2002.

PstS7 (termed “Warrior”) represents an incursion of a *P. striiformis* genetic group into Europe from a likely origin in the near-Himalayan region in Asia, which became widespread in several European countries already in its first year of detection in 2011 [37,38], and later spreading to additional countries in southern and eastern Europe and northern Africa. A distinctly different group, PstS8, followed the same path although less widespread. Altogether these groups largely replaced the pre-existing European yellow rust population within a couple of years, rendering previously resistant wheat cultivars susceptible or partly susceptible, and a number of previously rust susceptible cultivars more resistant [39]. In 2015, PstS7 was first detected in South America without giving rise to epidemics at that time (GRRC, <https://agro.au.dk/forskning/internationale-platforme/wheatrust/yellow-rust-tools-maps-and-charts/genetic-groups-frequency-map>).

The incursion of PstS13 into Argentina in 2017 is well documented, where it gave rise to the most widespread and severe epidemics of yellow rust on wheat since 1930 [40]. PstS13 was first detected in Australia in 2018, where it became dominant within a couple of years [17]. Although the evolutionary origin of PstS13 has not been confirmed, it was first detected in Europe in 2015, where multiple countries were affected (GRRC, <https://agro.au.dk/forskning/internationale-platforme/wheatrust/yellow-rust-tools-maps-and-charts/genetic-groups-frequency-map>). PstS13 isolates from these three continents shared the same multi-locus genotype and recovered isolates from Argentina and Europe shared virulence phenotype, suggesting a very recent common origin. In Argentina, PstS14 representing a less frequent genetic group, was occasionally detected along with PstS13, and in Australia PstS10 was detected already in 2017. PstS10 was first detected in Europe in 2012 (originally grouped as MLGW6 in [38]), after which it became prevalent in multiple European countries, whereas PstS14 was detected in Europe and northwest Africa in 2015-2016 (GRRC, <https://agro.au.dk/forskning/internationale-platforme/wheatrust/yellow-rust-tools-maps-and-charts/genetic-groups-frequency-map>). Altogether, the cases of PstS7, PstS10, PstS13 and PstS14 probably represent the most significant cereal rust LDD events since the world-wide spread of PstS1/PstS2 around year 2000.

The risks of spread of yellow rust from East Africa to the Arabian Peninsula and onwards to South Asia and spread of stem rust such as Ug99 along the same route have often been referred to [21,22]. However, at least three recent incursions of yellow rust into East Africa suggest migration in the opposite direction (GRRC, <https://agro.au.dk/forskning/internationale-platforme/wheatrust/news-and-events/news-item/artikel/grrc-report-of-yellow-and-stem-rust-genotyping-and-race-analyses-2021>), which has not yet been considered in spore dispersal modeling studies [23]. PstS6 was first detected in Ethiopia in 2010 during the severe yellow rust epidemics on the two most widely grown wheat cultivars in the country [41]). These cultivars were subsequently replaced by yellow rust resistant cultivars and the number of epidemic sites dropped until the incursion of PstS11, which was detected in Ethiopia in 2016, after which it became dominant in several East African countries. The third incursion into Ethiopia, caused by PstS16, was detected in autumn 2020. Up to 2009, PstS6 was observed in samples from multiple locations in Afghanistan, PstS11 and PstS16 were first detected in Asia in 2012 and 2017, respectively, and none of these groups have to date been detected outside South/Central Asia and East Africa.

In comparison, incursions of wheat stem rust at the inter-continental scale appear to have been less frequent (Figure 1B). For instance, Ug99 races of stem rust evolving since 1999 have not been observed outside Africa, except for sporadic cases in Iran and Yemen [42]. However, three different and distinct genetic groups have been observed in multiple countries in Europe since 2016,

previously detected in the Caucasian area and West Asia [43]). The detection across multiple sites in southern Europe in 2016-2017 suggests transmission by airborne spores originating from areas south and east of Europe. A high proportion of stem rust susceptible wheat cultivars and increasingly favorable environment for stem rust facilitated additional spread and establishment across wide geographical areas in central and western Europe [7,44].

The immediate source areas for LDD events involving rust fungi have often been dominated by clonal populations, with the exception of the incursions of yellow rust PstS7/PstS8 from the near-Himalayan region into Europe [38] and stem rust Clade III-B into Europe, first detected in a recombining population in the Caucasian region [7,43]. However, sexual recombination, which in the case of rust fungi often requires an alternate host, as well as somatic hybridization events should not be underestimated as drivers of evolution of new variants [45-48].

Conclusion

While LDD events represent extraordinary cases, they reflect a trend towards an increasing risk of exotic (non-indigenous) incursions of plant pathogens and increasing number of cases where invasive species and strains have affected crop production. For instance, the number of non-indigenous plant pathogen species invading the USA per decade were tripled in the 1990s compared to 1940-1970 [49]; in Australia, nine foreign incursions of stem and leaf rust on wheat were observed between 1925 and 2005, of which seven occurred since 1969 [5]. The recent examples of global spread of wheat yellow rust and wheat stem rust presented in this review strongly underline this trend. However, irrespectively of entry pathway, LDD events of airborne pathogens are difficult to prevent and/or regulate via quarantine measures. Therefore, the most promising strategy to ensure plant health in relation to rust fungi may be increased preparedness by coordinated, global plant pathogen surveillance programs and mitigation efforts to reduce disease progress by strengthening plant breeding efforts towards 'durable' disease resistance, and promotion of host crop diversification and cultivar/species mixtures.

References and recommended reading

1. Dillon CF, Dillon MB, Drake HL: **Multiscale Airborne Infectious Disease Transmission**. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 2021, **87**:e02314-02320.

** This comprehensive review of airborne infectious disease transmission includes examples of airborne plant, animal and human diseases. The authors list examples of airborne transmission at near range (<5m), medium range (50-500m), long range (500-500 km) and continental range (>500 km). Examples of transmission at continental range includes both plant- and human pathogens. The underestimation of these events and the low priority given to these until the recent COVID-19 outbreak are discussed

2. Brown JKM, Hovmøller MS: **Aerial Dispersal of Pathogens on the Global and Continental Scales and Its Impact on Plant Disease**. *Science* 2002, **297**:537-541.
3. Carvajal-Yepes M, Cardwell K, Nelson A, Garrett KA, Giovani B, Saunders DGO, Kamoun S, Legg JP, Verdier V, Lessel J, et al.: **A global surveillance system for crop diseases**. *Science* 2019, **364**:1237-1239.
4. van Dijk M, Morley T, Rau ML, Saghay Y: **A meta-analysis of projected global food demand and population at risk of hunger for the period 2010–2050**. *Nature Food* 2021, **2**:494-501.

5. Park RF, Fetch T, Hodson D, Jin Y, Nazari K, Prashar M, Pretorius ZA: **International surveillance of wheat rust pathogens, progress and challenges**. In *BGRI 2010 Technical Workshop 30-31 May 2010*; St Petersburg: Borlaug Global Rust Initiative: 2010:22-32.
6. Hovmøller MS: **The increased risk of global wheat rust pandemics: putting yellow rust into perspective**. In *Fungal Diseases: An Emerging Threat to Human, Animal, and Plant Health*. Edited by Eds L. Olsen ERC, D.A. Relman and L. Pray: The National Academic Press; 2011:252–263.
7. Patpour M, Hovmøller MS, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Randazzo B, Villegas D, Shamanin VP, Berlin A, Flath K, Czembor P, Hanzalova A, et al.: **Wheat Stem Rust Back in Europe: Diversity, Prevalence and Impact on Host Resistance**. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 2022, **13**.

*This paper investigates the recent re-emergence of wheat stem rust at epidemic levels in Europe caused by three distinct genetic groups. Genotyping and phenotyping of almost 500 isolates sampled 2016-2021 from 17 European countries was compared with previous international studies that included Caucasia and West Asia, among others, suggested that airborne transmission of urediniospores from these areas was the most likely explanation. In addition, the study revealed high genetic diversity in local *P. graminis* populations on wheat in proximity to the alternate host, *Berberis* spp., which may serve as source for the emergence of new aggressive strains in Europe and beyond.

8. MacLeod A, Pautasso M, Jeger MJ, Haines-Young R: **Evolution of the international regulation of plant pests and challenges for future plant health**. *Food Security* 2010, **2**:49-70.
9. Pretorius ZA, Singh RP, Wagoire WW, Payne TS: **Detection of Virulence to Wheat Stem Rust Resistance Gene Sr31 in *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. tritici in Uganda**. *Plant Disease* 2000, **84**:203-203.
10. Singh RP, Singh PK, Rutkoski J, Hodson DP, He X, Jørgensen LN, Hovmøller MS, Huerta-Espino J: **Disease Impact on Wheat Yield Potential and Prospects of Genetic Control**. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 2016, **54**:303-322.
11. Hovmøller MS, Walter S, Justesen AF: **Escalating Threat of Wheat Rusts**. *Science* 2010, **329**:369-369.
12. Walter S, Ali S, Kemen E, Nazari K, Bahri B, Enjalbert J, Brown JK, Sicheritz-Pontén T, Jones J, de Vallvieuille-Pope C, et al.: **Molecular markers for tracking the origin and worldwide distribution of invasive strains of *Puccinia striiformis***. *Ecology and Evolution* 2016, doi: **10.1002/ece3.2069**.
13. Dold M: **Top wheat experts call for scaling up efforts to combat Ug99 and other wheat rusts, 11 September 2009**. In *Eureka Alert*. Edited by: http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2009-09/bc-twe091009.php; 2009.
14. McIntosh RA, Pretorius ZA: **Borlaug Global Rust Initiative provides momentum for wheat rust research**. *Euphytica* 2011, **179**:1-2.
15. Isard SA, Gage SH, Comtois P, Russo JM: **Principles of the Atmospheric Pathway for Invasive Species Applied to Soybean Rust**. *BioScience* 2005, **55**:851-861.
16. Wellings CR, McIntosh RA, Walker J: ***Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. tritici in Eastern Australia possible means of entry and implications for plant quarantine**. *Plant Pathology* 1987, **36**:239-241.
17. Ding Y, Cuddy WS, Wellings CR, Zhang P, Thach T, Hovmøller MS, Qutob D, Brar GS, Kutcher HR, Park RF: **Incursions of divergent genotypes, evolution of virulence and host jumps shape a continental clonal population of the stripe rust pathogen *Puccinia striiformis***. *Molecular Ecology* 2021, **30**:6566-6584.

** Through a combination of genome sequencing, virulence phenotyping and comparison to already defined genetic groups by microsatellite genotyping, a selection of yellow rust isolates from the

Australian nationwide surveys were assigned to genetic groups that were previously prevalent at other continents. This confirmed the historic incursion of the yellow rust disease from Europe in 1979, a new incursion of a specific genetic group in 2002 (from East Africa/North America), and the incursion of two additional genetic groups in 2017-2018 that were first detected in Europe 2-5 years earlier. This study confirms that the contemporary Australian *P. striiformis* population is strongly influenced by periodic incursions from other continents.

18. Visser B, Meyer M, Park RF, Gilligan CA, Burgin LE, Hort MC, Hodson DP, Pretorius ZA: **Microsatellite Analysis and Urediniospore Dispersal Simulations Support the Movement of *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. tritici from Southern Africa to Australia.** *Phytopathology*® 2019, **109**:133-144.
 19. Kolmer JA, Mirza JI, Imtiaz M, Shah SJA: **Genetic Differentiation of the Wheat Leaf Rust Fungus *Puccinia triticina* in Pakistan and Genetic Relationship to Other Worldwide Populations.** *Phytopathology*® 2017, **107**:786-790.
 20. Kolmer JA, Ordoñez ME, German S, Morgounov A, Pretorius Z, Visser B, Goyeau H, Anikster Y, Acevedo M: **Multilocus Genotypes of the Wheat Leaf Rust Fungus *Puccinia triticina* in Worldwide Regions Indicate Past and Current Long-Distance Migration.** *Phytopathology*® 2019, **109**:1453-1463.
- ** This paper presents the first comprehensive study of *Puccinia triticina* at a global scale. The genetic relationship of more than 800 pathogen isolates from 11 regions worldwide were studied using microsatellite markers and race phenotyping. All populations had features of clonal reproduction, and several isolates sampled across different continental regions and time spans had identical or highly related multilocus genotypes indicating past and more recent migration events.
21. Sharma-Poudyal D, Chen X, Wan AM, Zhan GM, Kang ZS, Cao SQ, Jin SL, Morgounov A, Akin B, Mert Z, et al.: **Virulence characterization of international collections of the wheat stripe rust pathogen, *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. tritici.** *Plant Disease* 2013, **97**:379-386.
 22. Ali S, Gladieux P, Leconte M, Gautier A, Justesen AF, Hovmoller MS, Enjalbert J, De Vallavieille-Pope C: **Origin, migration routes and worldwide population genetic structure of the wheat yellow rust pathogen *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. tritici.** *PLOS Pathogens* 2014, **10**:e1003903.
 23. Meyer M, Cox JA, Hitchings MDT, Burgin L, Hort MC, Hodson DP, Gilligan CA: **Quantifying airborne dispersal routes of pathogens over continents to safeguard global wheat supply.** *Nature Plants* 2017, **3**:780-786.
 24. Meyer M, Burgin L, Hort MC, Hodson DP, Gilligan CA: **Large-Scale Atmospheric Dispersal Simulations Identify Likely Airborne Incursion Routes of Wheat Stem Rust Into Ethiopia.** *Phytopathology*® 2017, **107**:1175-1186.
 25. Huang M, Liu T, Cao S, Yuen J, Zhan J, Jia Q, Gao L, Liu B, Chen W, Berlin A: **Analyses of Wheat Yellow Rust Populations Reveal Sexual Recombination and Seasonal Migration Pattern of *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. tritici in Gangu, Northwestern China.** *Phytopathology*® 2021, **111**:2268-2277.
 26. Liang J, Liu X, Tsui CKM, Ma Z, Luo Y: **Genetic Structure and Asymmetric Migration of Wheat Stripe Rust Pathogen in Western Epidemic Areas of China.** *Phytopathology*® 2021, **111**:1252-1260.
 27. Chen W, Wellings C, Chen X, Kang Z, Liu T: **Wheat stripe (yellow) rust caused by *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. tritici.** *Mol Plant Pathol* 2014, **15**:433 - 446.
 28. Milus EA, Kristensen K, Hovmoller MS: **Evidence for Increased Aggressiveness in a Recent Widespread Strain of *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp tritici Causing Stripe Rust of Wheat.** *Phytopathology* 2009, **99**:89-94.
 29. Chen XM: **Epidemiology and control of stripe rust *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp tritici on wheat.** *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology-Revue Canadienne De Phytopathologie* 2005, **27**:314-337.

30. Wellings CR, Wright DG, Keiper F, Loughman R: **First detection of wheat stripe rust in Western Australia: evidence for a foreign incursion.** *Australasian Plant Pathology* 2003, **32**:321-322.
31. Hovmøller MS, Yahyaoui AH, Milus EA, Justesen AF: **Rapid global spread of two aggressive strains of a wheat rust fungus.** *Molecular Ecology* 2008, **17**:3818-3826.
32. Wellings CR: **Puccinia striiformis in Australia: a review of the incursion, evolution, and adaptation of stripe rust in the period 1979-2006.** *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research* 2007, **58**:567-575.
33. Brar GS, Ali S, Qutob D, Ambrose S, Lou K, Maclachlan R, Pozniak CJ, Fu YB, Sharpe AG, Kutcher HR: **Genome re-sequencing and simple sequence repeat markers reveal the existence of divergent lineages in the Canadian Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici population with extensive DNA methylation.** *Environ Microbiol* 2018, **20**:1498-1515.
34. Hovmøller MS: **Sources of seedling and adult plant resistance to Puccinia striiformis f.sp. tritici in European wheats.** *Plant Breeding* 2007, **126**:225-233.
35. de Vallavieille-Pope C, Ali S, Leconte M, Enjalbert J, Delos M, Rouzet J: **Virulence dynamics and regional structuring of Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici in France between 1984 and 2009.** *Plant Disease* 2012, **96**:131-140.
36. Wamalwa MN, Wanyera R, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Boyd LA, Owuochi J, Ogenido J, Bhavani S, Uauy C, Justesen AF, Hovmøller M: **Distribution of Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici Races and Virulence in Wheat Growing Regions of Kenya from 1970 to 2014.** *Plant Disease* 2022, **106**:701-710.
37. Hubbard A, Lewis C, Yoshida K, Ramirez-Gonzalez R, de Vallavieille-Pope C, Thomas J, Kamoun S, Bayles R, Uauy C, Saunders D: **Field pathogenomics reveals the emergence of a diverse wheat yellow rust population.** *Genome Biology* 2015, **16**:23.
38. Hovmøller MS, Walter S, Bayles RA, Hubbard A, Flath K, Sommerfeldt N, Leconte M, Czembor P, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Thach T, et al.: **Replacement of the European wheat yellow rust population by new races from the centre of diversity in the near-Himalayan region.** *Plant Pathology* 2016, **65**:402-411.
39. Sørensen C, Hovmøller MS, Leconte M, Dedryver F, de Vallavieille-Pope C: **New races of Puccinia striiformis found in Europe reveal race-specificity of long-term effective adult plant resistance in wheat.** *Phytopathology* 2014, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-12-13-0337-R>
40. Anibal Carmona M, Jose Sautua F, Perez-Hernandez O, Grosso C, Vettorello L, Milanese B, Corvi E, Almada G, Hovmøller MS: **Rapid emergency response to yellow rust epidemics caused by newly introduced lineages of Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici in Argentina.** *Tropical Plant Pathology* 2019, **44**:385-391.
41. Jaleta M, Hodson D, Abeyo B, Yirga C, Erenstein O: **Smallholders' coping mechanisms with wheat rust epidemics: Lessons from Ethiopia.** *PloS one* 2019, **14**:e0219327.
42. Singh RP, Hodson DP, Jin Y, Lagudah ES, Ayliffe MA, Bhavani S, Rouse MN, Pretorius ZA, Szabo LJ, Huerta-Espino J, et al.: **Emergence and Spread of New Races of Wheat Stem Rust Fungus: Continued Threat to Food Security and Prospects of Genetic Control.** *Phytopathology* 2015, **105**:872-884.
43. Olivera PD, Sikharulidze Z, Dumbadze R, Szabo LJ, Newcomb M, Natsarishvili K, Rouse MN, Luster DG, Jin Y: **Presence of a Sexual Population of Puccinia graminis f. sp. tritici in Georgia Provides a Hotspot for Genotypic and Phenotypic Diversity.** *Phytopathology™* 2019, **109**:2152-2160.
44. Lewis CM, Persoons A, Bebbler DP, Kigathi RN, Maintz J, Findlay K, Bueno-Sancho V, Corredor-Moreno P, Harrington SA, Kangara N, et al.: **Potential for re-emergence of wheat stem rust in the United Kingdom.** *Communications Biology* 2018, **1**.
45. Villegas D, Bartaula R, Cantero-Martínez C, Luster D, Szabo L, Olivera P, Berlin A, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Hovmøller MS, McIntosh R, et al.: **Barberry plays an active role as an alternate host of Puccinia graminis in Spain.** *Plant Pathology* 2022, **71**:1174-1184.

46. Zhao J, Wang M, Chen X, Kang Z: **Role of Alternate Hosts in Epidemiology and Pathogen Variation of Cereal Rusts**. *Annu Rev Phytopathol* 2016, **54**:207-228.
47. Li F, Upadhyaya NM, Sperschneider J, Matny O, Nguyen-Phuc H, Mago R, Raley C, Miller ME, Silverstein KAT, Henningsen E, et al.: **Emergence of the Ug99 lineage of the wheat stem rust pathogen through somatic hybridisation**. *Nature Communications* 2019, **10**:5068.
48. Rodriguez-Algaba J, Hovmøller MS, Villegas D, Cantero-Martínez C, Jin Y, Justesen AF: **Two Indigenous Berberis Species From Spain Were Confirmed as Alternate Hosts of the Yellow Rust Fungus Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici**. *Plant Disease* 2021, **105**:2281-2285.

* This paper demonstrates that two *Berberis* species indigenous to Spain can serve as alternate host of *P. striiformis* under experimental conditions. So far, no indications of sexual reproduction of *P. striiformis* in Europe has been observed, but the study highlights the potential role of *Berberis* species for generating new variability in *P. striiformis*.

49. Scherm H, Coakley SM: **Plant pathogens in a changing world**. *Australasian Plant Pathology* 2003, **32**:157-165.
50. Thach T, Ali S, de Vallavieille-Pope C, Justesen AF, Hovmøller MS: **Worldwide population structure of the wheat rust fungus Puccinia striiformis in the past**. *Fungal Genetics and Biology* 2016, **87**:1-8.

Figure 1 legend. Documented inter-continental incursions of wheat rust fungi since 2000, *Puccinia striiformis* (1A) and *P. graminis* (1B) based on sequential resampling of multi-locus genotypes. The within pathogen grouping is based on genotypic similarities, i.e., minor (or no) differentiation among individuals within a group, and distinct differentiation between groups (<https://agro.au.dk/forskning/internationale-platforme/wheatrust/yellow-rust-tools-maps-and-charts/definitions-of-races-and-genetic-groups>; [7]. Up to 2008, genotyping was generally based on Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphisms (AFLPs) [31], which was replaced by Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers according to [50] and [7]. A total of approximately 3000 *P. striiformis* samples from six continents, 1000 *P. graminis* samples from three continents, and multiple additional samples from cited and aligned studies were considered. Dotted circles represent putative source areas, arrows represent putative transmission routes, colored circles represent named genetic groups and first year of detection at a new continent.

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Declaration of interests

- The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.
- The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

B

- Clade III-B
- Clade IV-B
- Clade IV-F

Figure

